

Aromatic Diimine Dependent Structural Features of Iron(II), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes with some Tetradentate Schiff Base Ligands

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Complexes of iron(II), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) with four tetradentate (ONNO) Schiff base ligands viz salicylaldehyde *o*-phenylenediimine (Salophen) salicylaldehyde metaphenylenediimine (Salmphen), 2 hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde *o*-phenylenediimine (Nalophen) and 2 hydroxy-1 naphthaldehyde *m*-phenylenediimine (Nalmphen) are shown to have aromatic diimine dependent structural features. Although, Salophen complexes are known, complexes of Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with Salmphen, Nalophen and Nalmphen Schiff base ligands are prepared and characterised by various physicochemical and spectral studies. While Salophen and Nalophen give monomeric and low spin complexes the ligands prepared using metaphenylenediamine form binuclear complexes presumably due to longer chain length and less steric strain present in the latter ligands. The structural characterisation of a group of complexes are presented. In addition organocobalt complexes of Salophen and Nalophen are prepared and characterised.

Our recent survey of literature¹⁻¹⁰ on transition metal complexes of *cis*-N₂O₂ tetradentate ligands revealed that transition metal complexes with Schiff bases derived from aromatic carbonyls and aliphatic diamines are studied most. However, aromatic diamines are not used much for the preparation of analogous ligands and their transition metal complexes. Further, no attempt is made for the synthesis and characterisation of iron(II), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes with series of tetradentate Schiff bases, viz. salicylaldehyde *o*-phenylenediimine (Salophen), salicylaldehyde *m*-phenylenediimine (Salmphen), 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde *o*-phenylenediimine (Nalophen) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde *m*-phenylenediimine (Nalmphen).

Biggotto *et al.*¹⁰ prepared cobalt complexes in an attempt to derive extended model systems for vitamin B₁₂. Later some teradentate Schiff base cobalt complexes were characterised as oxygen carriers^{4,11}. The chemistry of manganese^{5,12}, iron¹³, nickel¹⁴ and copper¹⁵ complexes of Salophen does not have counter-part in present complexes of Salmphen, Nalophen and Nalmphen. The purpose of the present study is to present the aromatic diimine dependent structural properties of iron(II), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes with related tetradentate Schiff base ligands.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are stable at room temperature, non-hygroscopic, insoluble in water and many common organic solvents, but soluble in DMF and DMSO. The analytical and physical data of the complexes are presented in Table 1. The analytical data of the complexes indicate that the metal to ligand ratio is 1 : 1. The molar conductance values of the complexes in DMF are in the range

5–20 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ indicate their non-electrolytic nature¹⁶.

Magnetic moments of the iron(II) complexes of Salmphen and Nalmphen correspond to octahedral spin-free configuration while the iron(II) complexes of Salophen and Nalophen show low magnetic moments (0.98 and 1.16 B.M. respectively) assignable to low-spin octahedral complexes. Electronic spectral studies reveal that all the four iron complexes show charge transfer band with Fe^{II} electrons being transferred to empty π-type antibonding orbitals of the respective ligands. In addition, another band is also seen in high energy region assignable to π→π* azomethine absorption of ligands. These bands are shifted to higher wavelength with increased intensity in pyridine solvent indicating the formation of pyridine adducts in solution in analogy with previous observation¹³. The cobalt complex of Salophen was studied before by Biggotto *et al.*¹⁰. The magnetic moment of cobalt complexes of Salmphen, Nalophen and Nalmphen are 2.88, 2.35 and 2.80 B.M. respectively, in analogy with the reported magnetic values of known square-planar complexes^{17,18}. In the electronic spectra of the Co-Nalophen and Co-Nalmphen complex two strong bands are observed at (29 585, 29 850) and (24 875, 25 975 cm⁻¹) attributable to charge transfer bands. Strong bands at 19 605 and 21 505 cm⁻¹ in the electronic spectra of the Co-Nalophen and Co-Nalmphen complexes respectively, are observed in analogy with other square-planar complexes^{19,20}. Additional weak bands are also observed at 10 500 and 10 700 cm⁻¹ respectively, for the Nalophen and Nalmphen complexes characteristic of square-planar stereochemistry²¹. The electronic spectrum of Co-Salmphen complex gave no information as the weak spin-forbidden *d-d* transitions were fully covered by the tail of broad and strong CT band around 29 400 cm⁻¹.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm⁻¹) DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd. (Colour, yield %)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				ν _{OH}	ν _{C=N}	ν _{C=O}	ν _{M-O}	ν _{M-N}
	C	H	N	M					
Salophen (Orange, 69)	75.50 (75.80)	8.15 (8.05)	9.15 (8.85)	—	3 450	1 611	1 115	—	—
[Fe(Salophen)(H ₂ O) ₂] (Brown, 50)	56.48 (58.70)	4.26 (4.43)	6.59 (6.84)	14.05 (14.38)	3 166	1 609	1 115	493	398
Ni(Salophen) (Red, 53)	66.10 (64.30)	3.69 (3.78)	7.42 (7.50)	15.96 (15.73)	—	1 606	1 126	409	335
Salmphen (Brown, 70)	76.30 (75.86)	4.90 (5.05)	8.10 (8.86)	—	3 435	1 622	1 107	—	—
[Fe(Salmphen)(H ₂ O) ₂] (Brown, 41)	57.55 (58.70)	4.35 (4.43)	6.90 (6.84)	15.55 (14.38)	3 057	1 619	1 149	478	340
[Co(Salmphen)] ₂ (Brown, 57)	62.50 (64.35)	4.11 (3.78)	7.30 (7.50)	15.43 (15.78)	—	1 619	1 150	477	325
[Ni(Salmphen)] ₂ (Brown, 66)	65.65 (64.69)	3.83 (3.78)	7.45 (7.50)	15.95 (15.73)	—	1 620	1 150	478	335
Nalophen (Red, 65)	81.55 (80.67)	5.00 (4.80)	6.95 (6.72)	—	3 474	1 611	1 141	—	—
[Fe(Nalophen)(H ₂ O) ₂] (Brown, 66)	63.64 (66.03)	4.55 (4.35)	5.71 (5.49)	11.76 (11.55)	3 150	1 602	1 162	493	358
Co(Nalophen) (Brown, 52)	69.12 (71.04)	3.68 (3.83)	5.87 (5.91)	12.05 (12.44)	—	1 603	1 164	458	344
Ni(Nalophen) (Brown, 70)	72.95 (71.07)	3.90 (3.83)	6.99 (5.91)	12.54 (12.40)	—	1 603	1 172	430	340
Nalmphen (Brown, 34)	79.55 (80.67)	4.50 (4.80)	7.05 (6.72)	—	3 454	1 618	1 137	—	—
[Fe(Nalmphen)(H ₂ O) ₂] (Brown, 77)	67.50 (66.02)	4.23 (4.35)	5.45 (5.49)	12.10 (11.55)	3 155	1 600	1 160	458	340
[Co(Nalmphen)] ₂ (Brown, 43)	69.50 (71.04)	3.75 (3.83)	5.97 (5.91)	12.67 (12.44)	—	1 603	1 141	456	336
[Ni(Nalmphen)] ₂ (Brown, 45)	71.55 (71.07)	3.96 (3.83)	5.85 (5.91)	12.35 (12.40)	—	1 601	1 160	434	340
CH ₃ -Co(Salophen)Py (Brown, 37)	68.04 (66.81)	4.55 (4.74)	9.37 (8.98)	11.95 (12.60)	—	—	—	—	—
CH ₃ -Co(Nalophen)Py (Black, 61)	66.99 (71.95)	4.78 (4.61)	7.15 (7.40)	10.87 (10.38)	—	—	—	—	—

A five-coordinate cobalt complex with Salophen and its corresponding six-coordinate derivatives [CH₃-Co(Salophen)H₂O] and [CH₃-Co(Salophen)-THF] were reported^{7,10}. However, no report is made so far on the synthesis and characterisation of [CH₃-Co(Salophen)py] and [CH₃-Co(Nalophen)py] which may be regarded as model compounds for methylcobalamin. These organocobalt complexes of Salophen and Nalophen are diamagnetic corresponding to low-spin Co^{III} complexes. Electronic spectra (21 550, 25 125 for CH₃-Co(Salophen)py and 21 600, 26 880 cm⁻¹ for CH₃-Co(Nalophen)py) are also consistent with the idea that they have octahedral geometry. The most intense high energy band in the electronic spectra of these complexes have been assigned to π→π* transition²³ of equatorial ligand.

The Ni-Salophen and Ni-Nalophen complexes are diamagnetic suggesting square-planar configuration. These complexes display a band around 25 000 cm⁻¹ due to ¹A_{1g}→¹B_{1g}...(ν₂) transition. Electronic spectra of both the complexes in pyridine solvent suggest the presence of hexacoordinated nickel²³ which is evident by the appearance of additional weak band at 10 500 cm⁻¹ (ε, 70). Pyridine adducts are isolated and spectral measurements in toluene indicates that the reaction is reversed,

The nickel complexes of Salmphen and Nalmphen possess magnetic moment values of 3.57 and 3.79 B.M. respectively. As the magnetic moment values are greater than spin-only value, these complexes are assigned to have tetrahedral geometry²⁴. Thus the stereochemistry of the nickel complexes are diimine dependent present in Schiff base ligands. It may be presumed that the conformation of Schiff bases derived from *o*-phenylenediamine are different from those ligands using *m*-phenylenediamine. Typical tetrahedral complexes show bands at 16 000, 8 000 and 4 000 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ³T₁→³T₁(P)...(ν₃), ³T₁→³A₂...(ν₂) and ³T₁→³T₂...(ν₁ or 10 Dq) transitions respectively. In the present nickel complexes strong bands around 20 000 cm⁻¹ are observed due to ³T₁(F)→³T₁(P) transition²⁵. Due to strong electron delocalisation of the aromatic ring charge transfer bands, ν₃ transitions could not be detected in the electronic spectra of the present nickel complexes.

Infrared spectra: Important spectral bands for ligands and their metal complexes are presented in Table 1. The data suggest the participation of azomethine nitrogen atom and phenolic oxygen in complex formation. In the Fe^{II} complexes bands around 3 065 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν_{OH} stretching vibration of coordinated water molecules. Bonding of phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen atoms

is further corroborated by the appearance of M—O and M—N vibrations in the far-ir spectra of the metal complexes.

¹H nmr spectra : Pmr spectra were recorded for the nickel and organocobalt complexes. Multiplet signals correspond to aromatic protons and single absorption signal assignable to the presence of CH=N— protons : δ (DMSO-d₆; Me₄Si) Ni-Salophen, 6.35–7.25 (12H, m, phenyl), 8.25 (2H, s, =CH); Ni-Nalophen, 7.25–8.15 (16H, m, naphthyl and phenyl), 9.26 (2H, s, =CH); CH₃-Co (Salophen)py, 2.79 (3H, s, methyl), 8.97 (2H, d, py-2 and 6), 8.16 (1H, t, py-4), 7.96 (2H, d, py-3 and 5), 8.43 (2H, s, =CH-), 7.65–7.06 (12H, m, ArH); CH₃-Co(Nalophen)py, 2.27 (3H, s, methyl), 9.10 (2H, d, py-2 and 6), 8.06 (1H, t, py-4), 7.81 (2H, d, py-3 and 5), 8.59 (2H, s, =CH-), 7.73–7.16 (16H, m, ArH).

Molecular weights of the complexes indicate that Salophen and Nalophen forms mononuclear complexes while Salmphen and Nalmphen give binuclear complexes. Based on the results presented so far, square-planar structure for Ni-Salophen, Ni-Nalophen, Co-Nalophen, Co-Salmphen and Co-Nalmphen; tetrahedral structure for Ni-Salmphen complexes and octahedral structure for iron(II) complexes of all present tetradentate Schiff base ligands and organocobalt complexes are assigned.

It may be noted that Salmphen and Nalmphen which are derived from metaphenylenediamine form binuclear structure with Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II}. While the nickel complexes of Salophen and Nalophen ligands form square-planar complexes, that of Salmphen and Nalmphen give tetrahedral complexes. It may be presumed that due to longer chain-length, Salmphen and Nalmphen Schiff bases change their conformation to give tetrahedral and binuclear structure for the nickel complexes.

Based on the above discussion and information available in the literature, a variety of structural features of open-chain tetradentate Schiff base (containing aromatic diimine) complexes are summarised here. (i) Schiff bases derived from *o*-phenylenediamine give either mono-meric [Ni-Salophen] or dimeric [Cu-Salophen] complexes (1 and 2). Dimeric structures are facilitated by stacking between metal and phenolic oxygen. (ii) Binuclear structures (3) for Salmphen and Nalmphen complexes are possible due to longer chain-length and less steric strain present in these ligands. (iii) While Salophen and Nalophen give monomeric low-spin iron(II) complexes, the ligands prepared using *m*-phenylenediamine form high-spin and binuclear complexes presumably due to longer chain and less steric strain present in Salmphen and Nalmphen.

Experimental

All reagents, metal salts and organic solvents used were of AnalaR grade. All Schiff base ligands

were prepared by refluxing equimolar amounts of aromatic diamine and suitable aldehyde for 2 h.

Synthesis of complexes : A mixture of etharolic solution of the ligand (0.04 mol; 100 ml) and aqueous metal salt (0.04 mol; 100 ml) was refluxed under nitrogen atmosphere for 3–6 h. It was then cooled and the resulting solid was washed with cold methanol and finally with hexane. In the preparation of the iron(II) complexes the solvents were thoroughly bubbled with nitrogen gas before mixing and the reaction mixture was refluxed under nitrogen atmosphere for preventing the oxidation of metal ion.

The organocobalt complexes were prepared by following the reported procedure²⁶. A suspension of the ligand (0.01 mol) and cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate (0.01 mol) in methanol (50 ml) was stirred until the cobalt(II) salt dissolved. Then NaOH (1 g) and pyridine were added to it and cooled to –3° followed by addition of NaOH (0.5 g). Sodium borohydride (0.5 g) in water (5 ml) was added to it in small portion to avoid excessive foaming, followed by dimethyl sulphate (1.7 g, 0.01 mol) and the reaction mixture was allowed to warm gradually to room temperature. Finally water (250 ml) containing pyridine (1 ml) was added to give a brown precipitate which was washed several times with water and hexane. All the complexes were dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl₂.

The metal contents were determined using the standard procedures²⁷. Molecular weight was determined by using cryoscopic method in dimethylformamide. Molar conductivity, magnetic moments, electronic, infrared and ¹H nmr spectra were obtained as described earlier^{28–30}.

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